
**Milestone M-WP3.1 “End of
the first round of OHEJP
projects”**

OHEJP JIP MATRIX – WP3

Responsible Partner: 21-APHA, 34-PIWET

Other contributors: 13-SSI

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Leader	21-APHA, 34-PIWET
Other contributors	13-SSI
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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WHO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OIE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): as per OHEJP dissemination plan Social Media: as per OHEJP dissemination plan <u>Other recipient(s):</u> n.a.

MILESTONE M-WP3.1

“END OF THE FIRST ROUND OF OHEJP PROJECTS”¹

Summary

The One Health European Joint programme (OHEJP) Joint Integrative Project (JIP) “MATRIX: Connecting dimensions in One-Health surveillance” aims to link existing cross-sectorial One Health programmes in European countries, including animal health, public health and food safety. To advance in the implementation of One Health Surveillance (OHS) in practice, MATRIX values existing resources and creates synergies across sectors. The project proposes tailored solutions for European countries that want to advance the implementation of OHS.

MATRIX builds upon the work of many OHEJP JIPs of the first round, like JIP ORION and JIP COHESIVE among others. While they primarily focused on knowledge sharing and communication at the end of the surveillance pathway (surveillance outputs), MATRIX addresses cross-sectorial collaborations along the whole surveillance pathway.

The original MATRIX project proposal defined a milestone around the end of the first round of OHEJP projects to capture and build upon their developments.

The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic delayed the completion of many of the first round of OHEJP projects and heavily affected MATRIX Work Plan, too. However, by the end of December 2021 all MATRIX Work Packages (WP) successfully managed to collect relevant information from the first round of OHEJP projects.

This work is now important to the continuation of MATRIX activities as described in the project’s Year 5 (2022) Work Plan.

How MATRIX is capitalizing the experience of the OHEJP projects of the first round – examples:

- MATRIX WP1 is further building on JIP ORION’s OH surveillance inventories. Also, the experience of JRP NOVA is considered within MATRIX WP1-Task-2 through ongoing interviews.
- In MATRIX WP5, the development of the Knowledge-Integration Platform (KIP) extends the OHS Codex that was developed in the JIP ORION project, which is now named “OHS Codex: The Knowledge integration platform”.
- MATRIX WP6 makes use of knowledge by JIP ORION (i.e. data sources that are public or shared across sectors) and JRP NOVA (i.e. automated routines for data analyses and visualisation) to work on “data for decision dashboards”.

¹ The original title of the Milestone is “*End of the first round of OHEJP projects: this will coincide with the end of the inventory and requirement analysis phase in most WPs*”. In the MATRIX original project proposal, this milestone is defined under the MATRIX Work Package (WP) 3, while it is relevant to all the project’s WPs.